

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe

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“Report on existing data storage centres”

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Background Information on WP4

Objectives of WP4

Systems approaches require the collection, integration and storage of large data sets from genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and other –omics fields as well as molecular imaging with the goal to model life processes. The aim of the Data Generation work package (WP4) is to develop the appropriate institutional infrastructure and scientific mentality to support the collection of high throughput quantitative data in the biomedical and biotechnology fields in a way that is fit for systems biology. The overall objective of WP4 is to translate the strategic vision developed in WP3 (Overall Infrastructure, Eligibility and Accessibility) into an infrastructure plan for the construction phase of ISBE. Specifically, this document aims:

- To document the existing physical infrastructures providing high throughput data generation of partner institutes in order to identify those that are relevant to ISBE.
- To develop a long-term, strategic vision of the role of high throughput data generation centres for systems biology research.
- To develop a distributed infrastructure prioritised plan to renovate existing infrastructures and build new infrastructures. To determine their contribution and impact on ISBE by constructing a roadmap of integrating relevant proposals for national and pan-European construction plans.
- To design and define standards and harmonise procedures in the operation and management of the data generation centres and to ensure implementation of harmonised and standardised operating practices among users in cooperation with WP2.
- To define the needs of the European scientific community regarding access to the Data Generation Centres.
- To develop a plan for the implementation of European access and to develop the strategies that will establish the rules for providing European access to the Data Generation Centres of ISBE (in cooperation with WP3).
- To assess the needs, survey existing solutions and define the future strategy for developing a distributed data storage infrastructure for systems biology that can efficiently cope with unprecedented data volume and will be linked closely to the data generation centres and modelling hubs of ISBE (in cooperation with WP2 and WP3).

Relationship of WP4 to other work packages:

WP4 aligns closely with the following WPs:

- WP1 Project Management and Co-ordination: WP1 and WP3 will work together on the cross-cutting topics and responsibilities to integrate results and information of all WPs to generate the overall concept of ISBE.
- WP2 Model and Data Management: Considerations around the model and data management are a central topic for the overall ISBE concept, e.g. standardisation and SOPs have a high relevance and influence the strategy

- development how cooperation with other infrastructures, projects or initiatives might be implemented.
- WP3 Overall Infrastructure, Eligibility and Accessibility: This is a core activity of ISBE and is therefore vital for the vision, strategy and even advocacy of ISBE. Also the definition of the ISBE user concepts mainly dependent on the WP3 results.
 - WP5 Community Building and Synergies: Synergy and interaction with different projects, infrastructures and communities are vital for ISBE, for the preparatory phase the interaction with the different user/provider communities is highly important to optimise the concept and strategy plan for ISBE.
 - WP8 Modelling Infrastructure and Expertise: Input of WP8 is required on the definition of the modelling for the ISBE vision.
 - WP9 Technology and Science Watch: Input of WP9 is required to incorporate new technologies and applications to Data Generation Centres.
 - WP10 Training and Education: Together with WP10, WP7 will provide a strategic basis for identification of educational needs across fields in Europe.
 - WP11 Funding, Governance and Legal: WP7 will feed into WP11 with respect to the definition of funding needs and strategies, as well as with respect to advocacy at the level of funding agencies and governance.
 - WP13 Connections: On the vision of the essential role that the connections between centres and between centres and users play in achieving the integrative aims of ISBE.
 - WP15 Innovation, Impact and Exploitation: Liaison with WP15 to assist in providing information for the pipeline for technology and methodology exploitation and IP management, as well as a European expertise and technology matrix; the results of WP15 will also feed back to the WP3 centre structure discussion and the overall concept.

What is systems biology?

Systems Biology is an integrated experimental, informational, and computational science aiming to understand the dynamics of living systems. It has benefited from advances in fields such as genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and others that employ high throughput technologies and is driven by innovations in mathematics, computational analysis and simulation. Biologists may now pay more attention to understand how biological components work together to produce system behaviours rather than focusing exclusively on the properties of individual molecules and pathways. The adoption of a systems approach is providing new knowledge in many areas of Life Sciences and biomedical research including cell dynamics and signalling networks, global metabolic fluxes, and responses to drugs (and guidance in their development). It is expected that new, fundamental rules governing systems behaviour at various organisational levels – and how these levels are integrated - will emerge from these studies. However, there continue to be significant conceptual, technological, and cultural challenges to the realisation of the systems biology goals. It is the purpose of ISBE to promote innovative responses to these challenges.

The Data Generation Centres

Currently, technological gaps exist in mathematics, computation and experimentation. These include lack of standards and quality control measures in data collection and software engineering. Growing volumes of data from diverse high throughput experiments provide unprecedented opportunities for computational biologists. However, a high level of heterogeneity in data quality and experimental conditions hampers data comparison, integration, and application in computational modelling. Similar issues exist in software development. The lack of software engineering standards and sufficient documentation has limited software re-use, resulting in unnecessary duplication of efforts, and difficulty in comparing one program to another. Experimentally, there is a demand for the development of novel (and low-cost) methodologies to miniaturise, standardise, and automate high throughput data collection such that computational models can be populated with data specifically selected for tests of those models. In some cases, measurements from single cells are of great value. It is particularly important to sample living systems dynamically, at multiple scales, if realistic models are to be constructed. The systems biology centres are encouraged to develop innovative approaches to address these and other technological challenges.

Building cohesive multi-disciplinary research teams by integrating expertise across traditional disciplinary boundaries at the institutional level is not a simple undertaking. A goal of this initiative is to encourage leadership in creating such teams. In the larger research community, there is a need for leadership to disseminate new knowledge and to reduce excessive overlap and redundancy in project selection and tool development. Centres are expected to promote communication, collaboration, and technology and data sharing. Another aspect to be nurtured is the dialogue between theory and experiment. Transforming data into systems knowledge and principles will require iterative cycles of data collection, model generation, and model testing. Thus, the goal is to develop continuous communication and feedback among experimentalists and theoreticians. Finally, the emergence of a new science demands an adequate, diverse workforce of appropriately trained scientists. The future leaders of systems biology research will be knowledgeable and skilled in both experiment and computation. Innovation in education, therefore, is a significant task of the Systems Biology Data Generation Centres.

Defining the Data Generation Centres

A first approach has been made to define the periphery of the Data Generation Centres. We adopted a three-pronged strategy for a Data Generation Centre by focusing on:

1. critical computational challenges arising from the development of new technologies – next-generation DNA sequencing
2. fundamental and long-term research pursuits – systems biology driven by heterogeneous data-intensive approaches, and
3. development of bioinformatics methods for advancing technologies

The goal of WP4 is to provide an integrated infrastructure to allow European scientists to collect high throughput biological data and to verify model systems using state-of-the-art technologies, including high throughput genomics and transcriptomics (DNA array systems, highly parallel DNA sequencers and advanced multiplexing technologies), advanced proteomics, metabolomics, high throughput imaging systems including microscopy, flow cytometry, automated cell analysis, etc. The ISBE Data Generation Centres will build on existing resources (physical infrastructure including buildings, large scale high throughput equipment, human resources, scientific and management expertise) distributed among partner institutes. These resources will provide the basis to develop a state-of-the-art distributed infrastructure to satisfy the needs of the European research and biotechnological communities for systems biology resources.

Development of a comprehensive plan for an integrated infrastructure of large-scale data facilities for systems biology

Systems biology generates data sets of unprecedented size and complexity and, additionally, a very large number of different data types which need to be linked and integrated for analysis and modelling. As transfer of these primary data over conventional internet connections is not yet feasible, a distributed infrastructure of local and regional large-scale data storage centres, with efficient links to data generation centres and modelling hubs, will be an integral part of the systems biology infrastructure. An integrated infrastructure of large-scale data facilities for systems biology will accelerate discovery and advance biological knowledge through expanded technologies and competencies for processing samples, adding functional information and integrating and displaying the data. The Data Generation Centres will also increasingly work with and facilitate user access to complementary community-developed resources, both those generating data (e.g., proteomic data) and those providing tools for data integration and analysis. What will continue to distinguish the ISBE facility will be resources for users that go far beyond those available in individual laboratories or core facilities, in both scale and diversity, and a clear focus on a specific set of large-scale community-driven projects of central relevance to ISBE missions. Given the explosive advances occurring in high throughput technologies, we expect that the technologies available at the ISBE Data Generation Centres will evolve, continually guided and supported by a dedicated staff of scientists working together with users to address important biological problems. Coupled with the ISBE transition into becoming a user facility with an expanded set of capabilities, it will also actively expand its user community. New communities of users will be encouraged around specific biological questions (e.g., plant-microbe interactions) and ecosystems. Completely new communities of scientists such as pathway engineers, structural biologists and nanotechnologists, will also be encouraged to exploit the ISBE's capabilities. These new communities of future users will be recruited through targeted on-site workshops and the participation in the meetings relevant to these communities.

The strategy for the identification of all EU/EFTA etc. databases, adopted was based on extensive web searches and on the fact that since the year 2000, every 1st of January, Nucleic Acids Research (NAR) publishes a special Database issue, containing articles on the most prominent databases in the field of Biology. We identified 1552 databases which are classified into 15 main subject categories.

The data from our searches were parsed and a relational database was created. From each website, the country of origin of each database has been identified, as follows: The databases whose server name has code top-level domains of EU or EU-collaborating states (eg .eu, .gr, .uk, .fr, .de, .tr, .il, etc) were considered "European". For numeric server IPs or servers with international top-level domains (e.g. .com, .org, .net, .info, .int, etc), only those servers that are physically located in the aforementioned european states were considered "European". We identified 586 databases of European origin (**see Table 1 for a detailed list**).

We followed the NAR database classification scheme:

- Nucleotide Sequence Databases:
 - International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaborations
 - Coding and non-coding DNA
 - Gene structure, introns and exons, splice sites
 - Transcriptional regulator sites and transcription factors
- RNA sequence databases
- Protein sequence databases
 - General sequence databases
 - Protein properties
 - Protein localization and targeting
 - Protein sequence motifs and active sites
 - Protein domain databases; protein classification
 - Databases of individual protein families
- Structure Databases
 - Small molecules
 - Carbohydrates
 - Nucleic acid structure
 - Protein structure
- Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
 - Genome annotation terms, ontologies and nomenclature
 - Taxonomy and identification
 - General genomics databases
 - Viral genome databases
 - Prokaryotic genome databases
 - Unicellular eukaryotes genome databases
 - Fungal genome databases
 - Invertebrate genome databases
- Metabolic and Signalling Pathways

- Prokaryotic genome databases
- Enzymes and enzyme nomenclature
- Metabolic pathways
- Protein-protein interactions
- Signalling pathways
- Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
 - Model organisms, comparative genomics
 - Human genome databases, maps and viewers
 - Human ORFs
- Human Genes and Diseases
 - General human genetics databases
 - General polymorphism databases
 - Cancer gene databases
 - Gene-, system- or disease-specific databases
- Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
- Proteomics Resources
- Other Molecular Biology Databases
 - Drugs and drug design
 - Molecular probes and primers
- Organelle databases
 - Mitochondrial genes and proteins
- Plant databases
 - General plant databases
 - Arabidopsis thaliana
 - Rice
 - Other plants
- Immunological databases
- Cell biology

Next, we analysed the data by sorting initially the databases by subject (**Figure 1**) and country of origin (**Figure 2**). The data clearly demonstrate that there is a wealth of genomic, protein, structure, and metabolic/signalling databases housed in European servers. More specialised databases such as organelle, immunological, etc. databases are also available in Europe. When the same data were sorted by the European country of origin we discovered that UK, Germany and France on the one hand, and Italy, Switzerland and Spain on the other hand, house over 75% of the European databases. Subsequently, we analysed the geographical origin of the databases of each subject, according to the NAR classification scheme (**Figure 3-Figure 17**). We conclude that UK, Germany and France house most of the main types of –omics databases. Other countries focus on more specialised databases.

Figure 1. Pie chart representing the subject distribution of all European –omics databases which are published in Database Special Edition of NAR. More than half are Genomics (non-vertebrate), Protein sequence, Structure and Metabolic and Signalling Pathways Databases. Another quarter are Human Genes and Diseases and Nucleotide Sequence and Human and other Vertebrate Genome databases.

Figure 2. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all European –omics databases which are published in Database Special Edition of NAR. More than half are in the UK and Germany. Another quarter are in France, Italy, Switzerland and Spain.

Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)

Figure 3. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Genomics databases (non-vertebrate). More than half are in the UK and France. Almost another quarter are in Germany.

Protein sequence databases

Figure 4. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Protein sequence databases. More than half are in the UK and France. Almost another quarter are in Germany. 3 quarters of them are in Germany, UK, France, Italy and Switzerland.

Structure Databases

Figure 5. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Structure databases. Almost three quarters are in Germany, UK and Italy.

Metabolic and Signaling Pathways

Figure 6. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Metabolic and Signalling Pathway databases. More than half are in Germany and the UK. Another on eighth is in France.

Human Genes and Diseases

Figure 7. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Human Gene and Disease databases. More than half are in the UK and Germany.

Nucleotide Sequence Databases

Figure 8. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Nucleotide Sequence databases. Half are in Germany and the UK. More than a quarter are in Spain, Italy and Switzerland.

Human and other Vertebrate Genomes

Figure 9. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Human and other Vertebrate Genome databases. Two thirds are in the UK and Germany.

Plant databases

Figure 10. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Plant databases. More than three quarters are in Germany, France and the UK.

RNA sequence databases

Figure 11. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all RNA sequence databases. Almost half are in Poland, Germany, and France.

Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases

Figure 12. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Microarray Data and other Gene Expression databases. Three quarters are in the UK, Germany, and France.

Other Molecular Biology Databases

Figure 13. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all other Molecular Biology databases. Two thirds are in Germany, the UK and Italy.

Immunological databases

Figure 14. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Immunological databases. Almost half are in the UK and another one third is in Germany, and France.

Organelle databases

Figure 15. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Immunological databases. One third is in Italy.

Proteomics Resources

Figure 16. Pie chart representing the geographical distribution of all Proteomics Resources. Half are in Germany, three eighths in the UK and one eighth in Switzerland.

Cell biology

■ Poland

Figure 17. There is only one European Cell biology database which is in Poland.

Characteristics of the Data Repositories and Databases of ISBE

Modern systems biology is inherently dependent on a variety of data to inform statistical inferences, mathematical modelling, and theoretical work. The ISBE thus should provide the appropriate data types, metadata structures, visualisation capabilities, and analysis and inference tools to enable critical synergy between computational sciences and more traditional experimental approaches. ISBE should focus on the acquisition, integration, and accessibility of a rich body of data. Effective use of the knowledgebase will require evolving standards to support emerging research themes. The DSCs must incorporate processes to receive, transmit, and update information; it also should contain protocols for documenting and assessing the state and quality of the system and its contents. In addition to hardware, software, and network capabilities, a broader view of the ISBE clearly reveals the need for sustained support of core personnel with scientific and information technology expertise.

To better understand ISBE DCSs requirements relating to data and metadata, several critical issues must be addressed in collaboration with other WPs including (1) data and their generation by experimentation or simulation and modelling, (Task 4.2 of WP4) (2) the use of metadata for setting the context of data to enable their interpretation, (3) data handling (e.g., archiving, annotation, and maintenance), and (4) quality control and assurance (Data Stewardship and Availability).

Data Sources

In order to define better the DSCs we firstly identify the Data Sources. ISBE should support a wide variety of highly complex data from many sources, as our analyses have shown. These data must be comprehensively integrated and structured for further analyses and discovery. ISBE should gather or link to data from public and/or in house repositories, so users can perform complex queries and mathematical analyses. Effective integration with these and other external data sources is centrally important as institutions make rapid advances relating to many types of relevant data. As the primary data repository for ISBE projects, ISBE DSCs must effectively relate data from such projects to the growing wealth of external data and analytical tools. Inferred data, which are the products of modelling activities, comparative analyses, and simulations, are expected to become increasingly important components of the ISBE as its use among the scientific community grows.

We recommend the following key points to take into account for the DSCs:

- **Formal benchmarking.** Although no singularly integrative systems biology data bank currently exists, there are excellent best-in-class particular databases from which to draw examples. ISBE should benchmark data and information standards and, in certain cases, systems interoperability against best-in-class relevant data repositories.
- **Realistic scope and expectations.** ISBE data storage centres constitute an ambitious endeavour, requiring active participation by scientists. For example, using the DSCs data and services for scientific investigations and then feeding resultant data and knowledge back into the DSCs, when coupled with existing data management resources. Because of its anticipated scale, the DSCs should be developed in phases with consideration to existing, established data

management systems. The initial phase should support critical mission-relevant research and foundational science with well-defined needs and should provide resources to facilitate data access and ingestion. Implementation of these features would provide immediate value to the scientific community and would serve as a prototypic template for the DSCs expansion.

- **Development of a database of critical information.** The list of data entities provided above (Figs 1-17) will further be compiled and itemised for capture in ISBE. Next steps will focus on selecting and prioritising data types for ISBE inclusion should be critical first steps in defining system requirements. As part of its early activities, ISBE should further develop a database of the identified entities and include data types, data volumes, and current format standards. Database development could be facilitated by surveying Systems Biology principal investigators and establishing a website to collect survey data. The database should be reviewed regularly by the scientific community and perhaps be discussed and evaluated. Once database development is under way, data entities should be prioritized in terms of importance to the ISBE community and the challenges associated with incorporating the entities and establishing standards for each.
- **Metadata.** Regarding the Metadata related to the data in our approach the DSCs should incorporate them as well. The term “metadata” refers to information about data, such as how an experiment was performed, under what conditions (physiological or not) the experiments were performed, which organism/tissue/cell type/developmental stage was studied, and what methods were used for data analysis. Because metadata allow scientists to reproduce results, capturing metadata is vital for meaningful knowledgebase use among the scientific community. In many cases, metadata will follow existing community guidelines of minimum standards and ontologies set forth by community-driven efforts. Metadata management is a core capability that will allow integration of data generated from different technologies. Critical to the success of the ISBE DSCs are the following key elements:
 - Effective metadata management with common descriptions of data elements across multiple laboratories and investigators.
 - Common descriptive language for integrating data from multiple investigators (currently a limiting factor).
 - Metadata management tools that allow data generators to easily annotate and describe their data products and to extend metadata ontologies. For ISBE users to make comparisons among data and experimental results, each dataset from an environmental sample must be accompanied by metadata that provide contextual information. Such information would include, for example, the environment from which the sample was collected, methods used in collection and sample processing, types of analyses conducted on a given or nearby sample, and the overall sampling plan. At the lowest level of information submitted to ISBE DSCs data standards should

define the minimum metadata requirements that must accompany all submissions.

- Where appropriate, these standards should be provided with templates and tools to help data generators harvest metadata and plan experiments before data are collected.
- Much metadata should be collected before generating experimental data, but this process must be defined and prepared prior to conducting the experiment.
- Proper organization and capture of metadata are essential to providing the data context users require. Since collection of metadata often will be viewed as burdensome, effective standards describing required metadata must be established.

Supporting Creation, Storage, and Maintenance of Inferred Data

Inferred data will be produced by comparative analysis, modelling and simulation. Since one central goal of ISBE is to support derivation and validation of inferred data, the standards must be included for defining provenance, attachment of appropriate metadata, and integration with experimental data. More specifically:

- Accessing and using models to make and store inferences are emerging capabilities that increasingly more DSCs users will employ. The DSCs need to support not only development of subsystems and models but also access to the models themselves.
- Researchers will extract data entities from the DSCs, process them through analysis pipelines and workflows, and generate new entities that then will be submitted to the DSCs.
- The DSCs need to capture appropriate metadata and provenance information.
- The DSCs community should determine how to manage and control the introduction of inferred data and models.
- In addition to data, the DSCs need to provide software tools to ISBE community and link to other sites containing relevant software of interest. Such tools would include applications that facilitate capturing and recording inferred data and provenance.
- The DSCs should encourage open access to applications developed within the ISBE framework, thereby connecting the Systems Biology community.

Making Quality Control and Assurance Integral Parts of DSCs

Quality control (QC) and assurance (QA) are critical aspects of incorporating new data into the DSCs. Controlling quality occurs at the following two levels:

- QA establishes processes to ensure the quality of the overall experimental program that generates data flowing into the DSCs.
- QC screens data to reject faulty data.

These same quality processes can be applied effectively to inferred data and the mechanisms producing such data.

Existing data providers may have their own protocols to control the quality of their data. However, sources often provide processed data to users as a “black box,”

meaning little relevant metadata are easily accessible. Such metadata provide information on how data have been processed and normalised, including the tools, parameter values, and versions of resources used.

Another aspect of quality control involves changes to annotations and models.

Such changes often result from supporting evidence discovered through a tedious, manual curation process. Often, however, neither the process itself nor the evidence is propagated in a coupled way with annotation changes.

Managing data quality through QA processes and QC protocols and retaining and communicating information about such quality require the following:

- Data quality and information must be established for all data products and should be communicated with all exchanges of such products. This approach would enable users to efficiently complete evaluations of data products extracted for a specific use.
- Assembling and retaining quality information (e.g., QA processes and QC protocols) in a manner not overwhelming to data generators and consumers are significant topics to be resolved in the GKB design process.

The DSCs should provide a systematic approach for controlling the quality of data flowing into DSCs.

- Data must undergo appropriate QC protocols at their originating source. Although this responsibility for compliance lies with the source, the source also should provide metadata describing the data-processing workflow that can easily be queried, accessed, and summarized by ISBE users.
- Establishing QC standards and protocols as they relate to annotation and inference must be the responsibility and an essential component of the DSCs. Adhering to DSCs standards and implementing required protocols must be the responsibilities of data producers and users. Minimally, changes to data must be logged and detected conflicts updated and managed appropriately.
- ISBE infrastructure should enable users to access and contribute to the evidence behind each act of curation. For example, an assertion of the presence of a given variant of a subsystem should be accompanied by users' ability to relate it directly to phenotypic measurements, expression data, and the functions associated with a set of proteins and to record this ensemble as evidence supporting an annotation change. The real power of data integration is manifest in these capabilities, which represent a major step forward for systems research. As such, they should be integral parts of the ISBE process.
- The development of data standards often proceeds best within the auspices of international working bodies. ISBE should establish a strong policy of adopting existing standards and seeking out emerging ones. This policy will have advantages for users, helping them develop internal data standards, and may even lead to the DSCs spearheading efforts to promote community-wide standards.
- The DSCs should use best practices to build consensus on internal consistency of data collection and management.

- The DSCs will need a standards committee to define minimum requirements, recommend adoption of community-developed standards, and initiate drafting of DSCs standards as the need arises.
- This committee should be empowered to institute standards quickly and thus must establish a clear set of principles and decision-making processes to be followed.

Figure 18 shows a “heat map” of the geographical distribution of data bases useful for Systems Biology in Europe. It is quite clear that the majority of Systems Biology – related activities are housed in UK and Germany. A complete list of the European data bases is shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Database Name	URL	Country	Database Type
AREsite	http://rna.tbi.univie.ac.at/AREsite	Austria	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Effective	http://www.effectors.org	Austria	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FLYSNP	http://flysnp.imp.ac.at/	Austria	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
GOLD.db - Genomics Of Lipid-associated Disorders	http://gold.tugraz.at/	Austria	Human Genes and Diseases
ACLAME - A Classification of Mobile genetic Elements	http://aclame.ulb.ac.be/	Belgium	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
CATMA - Complete Arabidopsis Transcriptome MicroArray	http://www.catma.org/	Belgium	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases, Plant databases
European rRNA database	http://www.psb.ugent.be/rRNA/	Belgium	RNA sequence databases
LigASite	http://www.scmbb.ulb.ac.be/Users/benoit/LigASite/	Belgium	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Incipedia	http://www.Incipedia.org	Belgium	RNA sequence databases
pE-DB	http://www.pedb.vib.be	Belgium	Structure Databases
pico-PLAZA	http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/pico-plaza/	Belgium	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PlantCARE	http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/webtools/plantcare/html/	Belgium	Nucleotide Sequence Databases, Plant databases
PubMeth	http://matrix.ugent.be/pubmeth/	Belgium	Human Genes and Diseases
Quorumpeps	http://quorumpeps.ugent.be	Belgium	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
RTPrimerDB	http://medgen.ugent.be/rtprimerdb/	Belgium	Other Molecular Biology Databases
SNPeffect	http://snpeffect.switchlab.org	Belgium	Human Genes and Diseases
StrainInfo.net Biportal	http://www.StrainInfo.net/	Belgium	Other Molecular Biology Databases
TOPPR	http://iomics.ugent.be/toppr/	Belgium	Protein sequence databases
UMD-BRCA1/BRCA2 databases	http://www.umd.be/BRCA1/	Belgium	Human Genes and Diseases
AntiJen	http://www.ddg-pharmfac.net/antijen/Antijen/antijenhomepage.htm	Bulgaria	Immunological databases
DSD	http://www.ddg-pharmfac.net/dsd/DSD/dehydrog.htm	Bulgaria	Protein sequence databases
PPD	http://www.ddg-pharmfac.net/ppd/PPD/pKahomepage.htm	Bulgaria	Protein sequence databases
Database of Germline p53 Mutations	http://www.lf2.cuni.cz/projects/germline_mut_p53.htm	Czech Republic	Human Genes and Diseases
HERVd - Human Endogenous Retrovirus database	http://herv.img.cas.cz/	Czech Republic	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human Genes and Diseases
IRESite	http://www.iresite.org/	Czech Republic	RNA sequence databases
Mouse SAGE	http://mouse.img.cas.cz/sage/	Czech Republic	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
ChemProt	http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/ChemProt/	Denmark	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways

CycleBase	http://www.cyclebase.org/	Denmark	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases, Other Molecular Biology Databases
DistiLD	http://distild.jensenlab.org/	Denmark	Human Genes and Diseases
GenomeAtlas	http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/GenomeAtlas/	Denmark	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HemaExplorer	http://servers.binf.ku.dk/shs/	Denmark	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
NESbase	http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/databases/NESbase/	Denmark	Protein sequence databases
NetworkKIN	http://networkkin.info/	Denmark	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
O-GLYCBASE	http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/databases/OGLYCBASE/	Denmark	Protein sequence databases
SNAP	http://snap.humgen.au.dk/ or http://snap.genomics.org.cn/	Denmark	Human Genes and Diseases
Sulfolobus	http://www.sulfolobus.org/	Denmark	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
yApoptosis	http://www.ycelldeath.com/yapoptosis/	Denmark	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Fungal Genome Size Database	http://www.zbi.ee/fungal-genomesize/	Estonia	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Primer Studio	http://bioinfo.ebc.ee/PrimerStudio/	Estonia	Other Molecular Biology Databases
ADDA - A Domain Database	http://ekhidna.biocenter.helsinki.fi/sqgraph/pairsdb/	Finland	Protein sequence databases
BTKbase	http://bioinf.uta.fi/BTKbase/	Finland	Human Genes and Diseases
CanGEM	http://www.cangem.org/	Finland	Human Genes and Diseases
Dali database	http://ekhidna.biocenter.helsinki.fi/dali/start/	Finland	Structure Databases
Gene Expression in Tooth Database	http://bite-it.helsinki.fi/	Finland	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
KinMutBase	http://www.uta.fi/imt/bioinfo/KinMutBase/	Finland	Human Genes and Diseases
2P2ldb	http://2p2ldb.cnrs-mrs.fr/	France	Structure Databases
ABCdb	http://www-abcdb.biotoul.fr/	France	Protein sequence databases
AphidBase	http://www.aphidbase.com/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Atlas of Genetics and Cytogenetics in Oncology and Haematology	http://atlasgeneticsoncology.org/	France	Human Genes and Diseases
Axeldb	http://indigene.issb.genopole.fr/axeldb	France	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
BAlIBASE	http://bips.u-strasbg.fr/fr/Products/Databases/BAlIBASE2/index.html	France	Protein sequence databases
ButterflyBase	http://www.butterflybase.org/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
BYKdb	http://bykdb.ibcp.fr/	France	Protein sequence databases
CandidaDB	http://genolist.pasteur.fr/CandidaDB/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CATdb	http://urgv.evry.inra.fr/CATdb/	France	Plant databases
CAZy	http://www.cazy.org	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Colibri	http://genolist.pasteur.fr/Colibri/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Cyanolyase	http://cyanolyase.genouest.org	France	Protein sequence databases

Diatom EST Database	http://www.biologie.ens.fr/diatomics/EST/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Plant databases
EMGLib - Enhanced Microbial Genomes Library	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/emglib/emglib.html	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
ESTHER	http://bioweb.ensam.inra.fr/ESTHER/general?what=index	France	Protein sequence databases
euHCVdb	http://euhcvdb.ibcp.fr/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FLAGdb++	http://urgv.evry.inra.fr/projects/FLAGdb++/HTML/index.shtml	France	Plant databases
FusionDB	http://igs-server.cnrs-mrs.fr/FusionDB/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Protein sequence databases
GeneFarm	http://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/Genefarm/	France	Plant databases
GenoList	http://genolist.pasteur.fr/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Genomicus	http://www.dyogen.ens.fr/genomicus	France	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
GermOnline	http://www.germonline.org/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
GreenPhylDB	http://greenphyl.cirad.fr/	France	Plant databases
HBVdb	http://hbvdb.ibcp.fr	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HCVDB - Hepatitis C Virus Database	http://hepatitis.ibcp.fr/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HOINVGEN	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/databases/hoinvgen/HOINVGEN.html	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Hoppsigen	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/databases/hoppsigen.html	France	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
IARC TP53 Database	http://www-p53.iarc.fr/	France	Human Genes and Diseases
IMGT	http://www.imgt.org/	France	Immunological databases
IMGT/3Dstructure-DB	http://www.imgt.org/	France	Structure Databases
IMGT/GENE-DB	http://www.imgt.org/IMGT_GENE-DB/GENEelect?livret=0/	France	Immunological databases
IMGT/LIGM-DB	http://www.imgt.org/cgi-bin/IMGTlect.jv/	France	Immunological databases
IMGT/PRIMER-DB	http://www.imgt.org/	France	Other Molecular Biology Databases
INFEVERS	http://fmf.igh.cnrs.fr/infevers/	France	Human Genes and Diseases
InterEvol	http://biodev.cea.fr/interevol	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Interrupted coding sequences	http://www-bio3d-igbmc.u-strasbg.fr/ICDS/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
IRESdb - the Internal Ribosome Entry Site database	http://ifr31w3.toulouse.inserm.fr/IRESdatabase/	France	RNA sequence databases
Isfinder	http://www-is.biotoul.fr/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Nucleotide Sequence Databases
ITTACA	http://bioinfo.curie.fr/ittaca/	France	Human Genes and Diseases, Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
KBDOCK	http://kbdock.loria.fr/	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Knottin database	http://knottin.cbs.cnrs.fr/	France	Protein sequence databases
Manteia	http://manteia.igbmc.fr/	France	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes

MatrixDB	http://matrixdb.ibcp.fr/	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Metagrowth	http://igs-server.cnrs-mrs.fr/axenic/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
MicroScope	http://www.genoscope.cns.fr/agc/microscope/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
MitoGenesisDB	http://www.dsimb.inserm.fr/dsimb_tools/mitgene/	France	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases, Organelle databases
MolliGen	http://cbi.labri.fr/outils/molligen/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
NAPP	http://rna.igmors.u-psud.fr/NAPP	France	RNA sequence databases
Narcisse	http://narcisse.toulouse.inra.fr/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
NORINE	http://bioinfo.lifl.fr/norine/	France	Protein sequence databases
NRSub	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/nrsub/nrsub.html	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
ORENZA	http://www.orenza.u-psud.fr/	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
OryGenesDB	http://orygenesdb.cirad.fr/	France	Plant databases
Oryza Tag Line	http://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/OryzaTagLine/	France	Plant databases
P2CS	http://www.p2cs.org	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
ParameciumDB	http://paramecium.cgm.cnrs-gif.fr/db/index	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PeroxiBase	http://peroxibase.toulouse.inra.fr/index.php	France	Protein sequence databases
PhEVER	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/databases/phever/index.php	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PHYTOPROT	http://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/phytoprot/	France	Plant databases, Protein sequence databases
PlantRNA	http://plantrna.ibmp.cnrs.fr/	France	RNA sequence databases
Polymorphix	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/polymorphix/query.php	France	Human Genes and Diseases
PR2	http://SSU-rRNA.org	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
ProDom	http://prodom.prabi.fr/	France	Protein sequence databases
R.E.DD.B.	http://q4md-forcefieldtools.org/REDDB/	France	Structure Databases
RTKdb - Receptor Tyrosine Kinase database	http://pbil.univ-lyon1.fr/RTKdb/	France	Protein sequence databases
snoRNA-LBME-db	http://www-snorna.biotoul.fr/	France	RNA sequence databases
SpodoBase	http://bioweb.ensam.inra.fr/spodobase/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
SubtiList	http://genolist.pasteur.fr/SubtiList/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
TropGENE DB	http://tropgenedb.cirad.fr/	France	Plant databases
UniPathway	http://www.grenoble.prabi.fr/obiwarehouse/unipathway	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
ViralORFeome	http://www.viralorfeome.com/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
VirHostNet	http://pbildb1.univ-lyon1.fr/virhostnet/	France	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways

yMGV - Yeast microarray global viewer	http://www.transcriptome.ens.fr/ymgv/	France	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
2D-PAGE	http://www.mpiib-berlin.mpg.de/2D-PAGE/	Germany	Proteomics Resources
4DXpress	http://ani.embl.de/4DXpress/	Germany	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
AffinDB	http://pc1664.pharmazie.uni-marburg.de/affinity/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
AgeFactDB	http://agefactdb.jenage.de	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
AppaDB	http://appadb.eb.tuebingen.mpg.de	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
ARAMEMNON	http://aramemnon.botanik.uni-koeln.de/	Germany	Plant databases, Protein sequence databases
AthaMap	http://www.athamap.de/	Germany	Plant databases
AutoPSI	http://services.bio.ifi.lmu.de:1046/AutoPSIDB/	Germany	Structure Databases
BacDive	http://bacdive.dsmz.de	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
BRENDA	http://www.brenda-enzymes.org/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
BTO	http://www.brenda-enzymes.org/BTO/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CancerResource	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/cancerresource/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
CCSD - Complex Carbohydrate Structure Database (CarbBank)	http://www.glycome-db.org/getDownloadPage.action?page=carbbank	Germany	Structure Databases
CellFinder	http://www.cellfinder.org/	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
CellLineNavigator	http://www.medicalgenomics.org/celllinenavigator/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
Columba	http://www.columba-db.de	Germany	Structure Databases
ConsensusPathDB	http://cpdb.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
CORG - A database for COmparative Regulatory Genomics	http://corg.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Nucleotide Sequence Databases, RNA sequence databases
CORUM	http://mips.gsf.de/genre/proj/corum/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
CoryneRegNet	http://coryneregnet.cebitec.uni-bielefeld.de/v6/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Nucleotide Sequence Databases
CR-EST - Crop ESTs	http://pgrc.ipk-gatersleben.de/cr-est/	Germany	Plant databases
CSS - Carbohydrate Structure Suite	http://www.glycosciences.de/tools/	Germany	Structure Databases
CYGD - Comprehensive Yeast Genome Database	http://mips.gsf.de/genre/proj/yeast/index.jsp	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CyMoBase	http://www.cymobase.org/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
DARC	http://darcsite.genzentrum.lmu.de/darc/	Germany	Structure Databases
diArk	http://www.diark.org/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
DIMA	http://webclu.bio.wzw.tum.de/dima/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
DiProDB	http://diprodb.fli-leibniz.de/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases

DNAreplication.net	http://www.dnareplication.net/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
doRiNA	http://dorina.mdc-berlin.de	Germany	RNA sequence databases
DRC - Database of Ribosomal Crosslinks	http://www.molgen.mpg.de/~ag_ribo/ag_brimacombe/drc/defaultflow.html	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
DSMM - a Database of Simulated Molecular Motions	http://projects.villa-bosch.de/dbase/dsmm/	Germany	Structure Databases
DynaProt 2D	http://www.wzw.tum.de/proteomik/lactis/	Germany	Proteomics Resources
eggNOG	http://eggnog.embl.de/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
ELM	http://elm.eu.org/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
ELM - Eukaryotic Linear Motif: functional sites in eukaryotic proteins	http://elm.eu.org/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
EndoNet	http://endonet.bioinf.med.uni-goettingen.de/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases, Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Epitome	http://roslab.org/services/epitome/	Germany	Immunological databases
eProS	http://bioservices.hs-mittweida.de/Epros/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
FGDB	http://mips.helmholtz-muenchen.de/genre/proj/FGDB/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FlyView	http://flyview.uni-muenster.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FragmentStore	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/fragment_store	Germany	Structure Databases
FunSimMat	http://funsimmat.bioinf.mpi-inf.mpg.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
GABI-Kat SimpleSearch database	http://www.GABI-Kat.de/	Germany	Plant databases
GabiPD	http://www.gabipd.org/	Germany	Plant databases
GenColors	http://sgb.fli-leibniz.de/	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
GeneNest	http://genenest.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
GenePaint	http://www.genepaint.org/Frameset.html	Germany	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
GenomeRNAi	http://www.genomernai.org	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
GlycoMapsDB	http://www.glycosciences.de/modeling/glycomapsdb/	Germany	Structure Databases
GlycomeDB	http://www.glycome-db.org	Germany	Structure Databases
HoPaCI-DB	http://mips.helmholtz-muenchen.de/HoPI/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Human Phenotype Ontology	http://www.human-phenotype-ontology.org	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HuSiDa - Human siRNA database	http://itb.biologie.hu-berlin.de/~nebulus/sirna/index.htm	Germany	RNA sequence databases
HvrBase++	http://www.hvrbase.org/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases, Organelle databases
ITS2	http://its2.bioapps.biozentrum.uni-wuerzburg.de/cgi-bin/index.pl?about	Germany	RNA sequence databases, Structure Databases
JAIL	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/jail/	Germany	Structure Databases

Jenalib: Jena Library of Biological Macromolecules	http://www.fli-leibniz.de/IMAGE.html	Germany	Structure Databases
L1Base	http://line1.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
LEGER	http://leger2.gbf.de/cgi-bin/expLeger.pl	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
LIFEdb	http://www.dkfz.de/gpcf/lifedb.php	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
Lipase Engineering Database	http://www.led.uni-stuttgart.de/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
LocDB	http://www.rostlab.org/services/locDB/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
LOX-DB	http://www.glycosciences.de/spec/lox-db/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
MAMEP - Molecular Anatomy of the Mouse Embryo Project	http://mamep.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
MAPU	http://www.mapuproteome.com/	Germany	Proteomics Resources
MAtdB2	http://mips.helmholtz-muenchen.de/plant/athal/	Germany	Plant databases
MeGX	http://www.megx.net/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
MeMotif	http://projects.biotec.tu-dresden.de/memotif	Germany	Protein sequence databases
MEPD: A Medaka gene expression pattern database	http://ani.embl.de:8080/mepd/	Germany	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
MetaCrop	http://metacrop.ipk-gatersleben.de/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Plant databases
MethDB	http://www.methdb.de/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
METscout	http://metscout.mpg.de	Germany	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
MFunGD	http://mips.gsf.de/genre/proj/mfungd/	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
MIPS resources	http://mips.gsf.de/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
MIPSPplantsDB	http://mips.gsf.de/proj/plant/jsf/	Germany	Plant databases
MITOP2	http://www.mitop2.de/	Germany	Organelle databases
MNCDB	http://mips.helmholtz-muenchen.de/genre/proj/ncrassa/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Monosaccharide Browser	http://www.terravivida.com/vivida/monosaccharide/	Germany	Structure Databases
MOSDB	http://mips.gsf.de/proj/plant/jsf/rice/index.jsp	Germany	Plant databases
MP:PD	http://proteininformatics.charite.de/mppd	Germany	Protein sequence databases
Mpact	http://mips.gsf.de/genre/proj/mpact/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
mVOC	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/mvoc	Germany	Structure Databases
Negatome	http://mips.helmholtz-muenchen.de/proj/ppi/negatome	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Newt-omics	http://newt-omics.mpi-bn.mpg.de	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
NLSdb	http://rostlab.org/services/nlsdb/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
NMPdb - Nuclear matrix associated proteins database	http://www.rostlab.org/db/NMPdb/	Germany	Protein sequence databases

OGEE	http://ogeedb.embl.de	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
PDBselect	http://bioinfo.tg.fh-giessen.de/pdbselect/	Germany	Structure Databases
PEDANT	http://pedant.gsf.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PepX	http://pepx.switchlab.org/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
PhenomicDB	http://www.phenomicdb.de/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
PHOSIDA	http://www.phosida.com	Germany	Protein sequence databases
PhosPhAt	http://phosphat.mpimp-golm.mpg.de/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Plant databases
PlnTFDB	http://plntfdb.bio.uni-potsdam.de/	Germany	Plant databases
PoMaMo - Potato Maps and More	http://www.gabipd.org/projects/Pomamo/	Germany	Plant databases
Pristionchus.org	http://www.pristionchus.org/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
probeBase	http://www.microbial-ecology.net/probebase/	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
PRODORIC	http://prodoric.tu-bs.de/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Nucleotide Sequence Databases
PROMISCUOUS	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/promiscuous	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
ProSAS	http://services.bio.ifi.lmu.de/ProSAS/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases, Structure Databases
ProtChemSI	http://pcidb.russelllab.org/	Germany	Structure Databases
PTGL	http://ptgl.uni-frankfurt.de/	Germany	Structure Databases
PTMcode	http://ptmcode.embl.de	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
RB1 Gene Mutation Database	http://www.verandi.de/joomla/	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
RIDOM - Ribosomal Differentiation of Medical Microorganisms	http://www.ridom.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
RNA helicase Database	http://www.dexhd.org/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
S/MARt DB	http://smartdb.bioinf.med.uni-goettingen.de/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
SABIO-RK	http://sabiork.h-its.org/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Sebida	http://www.sebida.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
SelenoDB	http://www.selenodb.org/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
SelTarbase	http://www.seltarbase.org	Germany	Human Genes and Diseases
SILVA: a comprehensive online resource for quality checked and aligned ribosomal RNA sequence data	http://www.arb-silva.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
SIMAP	http://mips.gsf.de/simap/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
SMART	http://smart.embl-heidelberg.de	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Protein sequence databases
SpliceNest	http://splicenest.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases

STCDB - Signal Transduction Classification Database	http://bibiserv.techfak.uni-bielefeld.de/stcdb/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
STITCH	http://stitch.embl.de	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Strepto_DB	http://oger.tu-bs.de/strepto_db/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
StreptomeDB	http://streptomedb.pharmaceutical-bioinformatics.de	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
STRING	http://string.embl.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
SubtiWiki	http://subtiwiki.uni-goettingen.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
SuperCYP	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/supercyp	Germany	Protein sequence databases
SuperDrug	http://bioinf.charite.de/superdrug/	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases, Structure Databases
SuperHapten	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/superhapten/	Germany	Immunological databases
SuperNatural	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/supernatural/	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases, Structure Databases
SuperPain	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/superpain/	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
SuperScent	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/superscent/	Germany	Structure Databases
SuperSite	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/supersite/	Germany	Protein sequence databases
SuperSweet	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/sweet/	Germany	Structure Databases
SuperTarget	http://insilico.charite.de/supertarget/	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
SuperToxic	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/supertoxic/	Germany	Structure Databases
SWEET-DB	http://www.glycosciences.de/database/	Germany	Structure Databases
SynSysNet	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/synsysnet	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
SysPIMP	http://pimp.starflr.info/	Germany	Proteomics Resources
SYSTEMS	http://systems.molgen.mpg.de/	Germany	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
SYSTEMONAS	http://www.systemonas.de/	Germany	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
TassDB	http://www.tassdb.info/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
TFClass	http://tfclass.bioinf.med.uni-goettingen.de	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
TiProD	http://tiprod.bioinf.med.uni-goettingen.de/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Transformer	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/transformer	Germany	Other Molecular Biology Databases
tRNADB	http://trnadb.bioinf.uni-leipzig.de/	Germany	RNA sequence databases
UniCarbKB	http://www.glycosuite.com/	Germany	Structure Databases
UniHI	http://www.unihi.org/	Germany	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
uORFdb	http://cbdm.mdc-berlin.de/tools/uorfdb/	Germany	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
VBASE2	http://www.vbase2.org/	Germany	Immunological databases
Voronoia	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/voronoia/	Germany	Structure Databases

Voronoia4RNA	http://proteininformatics.charite.de/voronoia4rna/tools/v4rna/index	Germany	Structure Databases
CuticleDB	http://bioinformatics.biol.uoa.gr/cuticleDB/	Greece	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
DIANA-LncBase	http://www.microrna.gr/LncBase	Greece	RNA sequence databases
gpDB - G-protein database	http://bioinformatics.biol.uoa.gr/gpDB/	Greece	Protein sequence databases
OMPdb	http://aias.biol.uoa.gr/OMPdb/	Greece	Protein sequence databases
TarBase	http://microrna.gr/tarbase	Greece	RNA sequence databases
DoOP - Databases of Orthologous Promoters	http://doop.abc.hu/	Hungary	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
PDB_TM	http://pdbtm.enzim.hu/	Hungary	Structure Databases
TopDB	http://topdb.enzim.hu/	Hungary	Protein sequence databases
DARNED	http://beamish.ucc.ie/	Ireland	RNA sequence databases
GWIPS-viz	http://gwips.ucc.ie	Ireland	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
YGOB	http://wolfe.gen.tcd.ie/ygob/	Ireland	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
BitterDB	http://bitterdb.agri.huji.ac.il/bitterdb/dbbitter.php	Israel	Structure Databases
ConSurf-DB	http://consurfdb.tau.ac.il/	Israel	Structure Databases
Dynamic Proteomics	http://www.weizmann.ac.il/mcb/UriAlon/DynamProt/	Israel	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
eQuilibrator	http://equilibrator.weizmann.ac.il	Israel	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
EVEREST - EVolutionary Ensembles of REcurrent SegmenTs	http://www.everest.cs.huji.ac.il/	Israel	Protein sequence databases
GeneAnnot	http://genecards.weizmann.ac.il/geneannot/	Israel	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
GeneLoc	http://genecards.weizmann.ac.il/geneloc/	Israel	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
GeneNote	http://genecards.weizmann.ac.il/genenote/	Israel	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
GeneTide	http://genecards.weizmann.ac.il/genetide/	Israel	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
HORDE - Human Olfactory Receptor Data Exploratorium	http://bioportal.weizmann.ac.il/HORDE/	Israel	Human Genes and Diseases
LOQATE	http://www.weizmann.ac.il/molgen/loqate/	Israel	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PromEC	http://margalit.huji.ac.il/promec/	Israel	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Nucleotide Sequence Databases
ProTeus	http://www.proteus.cs.huji.ac.il/	Israel	Protein sequence databases
ProtoNet	http://www.protonet.cs.huji.ac.il/	Israel	Protein sequence databases
RepTar	http://reptar.ekmd.huji.ac.il/	Israel	RNA sequence databases
RsiteDB	http://bioinfo3d.cs.tau.ac.il/RsiteDB/	Israel	Structure Databases
SPIKE	http://www.cs.tau.ac.il/~spike/	Israel	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
TissueNet	http://netbio.bgu.ac.il/tissuenet/	Israel	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
TranspoGene	http://transpogene.tau.ac.il/	Israel	Nucleotide Sequence Databases

ASC - Active Sequence Collection	http://bioinformatica.isa.cnr.it/ASC/	Italy	Protein sequence databases
ASPicDB	http://www.caspur.it/ASPicDB/	Italy	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Benchmark	http://net.icgeb.org/benchmark/	Italy	Protein sequence databases
DG-CST	http://dgcst.ceinge.unina.it/	Italy	Human Genes and Diseases
DIGIT	http://www.biocomputing.it/digit4/	Italy	Immunological databases
DOMINO	http://mint.bio.uniroma2.it/domino/	Italy	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
eSLDB - eukaryotic Subcellular Localization database	http://gpcr.biocomp.unibo.it/esldb/	Italy	Protein sequence databases
HmtDB - Human Mitochondrial DataBase	http://www.hmtdb.uniba.it/	Italy	Organelle databases
HS3D - Homo Sapiens Splice Sites Dataset	http://www.sci.unisannio.it/docenti/rampone/	Italy	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Nucleotide Sequence Databases
HyperCLDB	http://bioinformatics.istge.it/hypercldb/	Italy	Other Molecular Biology Databases
KaryotypeDB	http://www.nenno.it/karyotypedb/	Italy	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
MetalPDB	http://metalweb.cerm.unifi.it/	Italy	Structure Databases
MINT	http://mint.bio.uniroma2.it/mint/	Italy	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
MitoDrome	http://mitodrome.ba.itb.cnr.it/	Italy	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Organelle databases
MitoRes	http://mitores.ba.itb.cnr.it/index.php	Italy	Organelle databases, Protein sequence databases
MitoZoa	http://mi.caspur.it/mitozoa/	Italy	Organelle databases
MMsINC	http://mms.dsfarm.unipd.it/MMsINC/	Italy	Structure Databases
MPDB - Molecular Probe Database	http://bioinformatics.istge.it/srs71m/	Italy	Other Molecular Biology Databases
Network of Cancer Genes	http://bio.ifom-ieo-campus.it/ncg	Italy	Human Genes and Diseases
Phospho3D	http://www.biocomputing.it/phospho3d/	Italy	Protein sequence databases, Structure Databases
PLANT-PIs	http://plantpis.ba.itb.cnr.it/	Italy	Plant databases, Protein sequence databases
PLPMDb	http://www.studiofmp.com/plpmdb/	Italy	Protein sequence databases
PMDB - Protein Model Database	http://www.caspur.it/PMDB/	Italy	Structure Databases
PPNEMA	http://www.ppnema.uniba.it/	Italy	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PRGdb	http://www.prgdb.org	Italy	Plant databases
REDIdb	http://biologia.unical.it/py_script/search.html	Italy	RNA sequence databases
RepeatsDB	http://repeatsdb.bio.unipd.it/	Italy	Structure Databases
SBASE	http://www.icgeb.org/sbase/	Italy	Protein sequence databases
SpliceAid-F	http://mi.caspur.it/SpliceAidF/	Italy	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
SURFACE	http://cbm.bio.uniroma2.it/surface/	Italy	Structure Databases
The Cell Cycle DB	http://www.itb.cnr.it/cellcycle/	Italy	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Other Molecular Biology Databases

TomatEST DB	http://biosrv.cab.unina.it/tomatestdb/	Italy	Plant databases
UCbase and miRfunc	http://ucbase.unimore.it/	Italy	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
UTRdb/UTRsite	http://utrdb.ba.itb.cnr.it/	Italy	Nucleotide Sequence Databases, RNA sequence databases
VirusMINT	http://mint.bio.uniroma2.it/virusmint/Welcome.do	Italy	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Crystallography Open Database	http://www.crystallography.net/	Lithuania	Structure Databases
Brix	http://brix.switchlab.org/	Netherlands	Structure Databases
EXProt	http://www.cmbi.kun.nl/EXProt/	Netherlands	Protein sequence databases
FUNPEP	http://swift.cmbi.kun.nl/swift/FUNPEP/gergo/	Netherlands	Human Genes and Diseases, Protein sequence databases
Gene Wiki	http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Portal:Gene_Wiki	Netherlands	Human Genes and Diseases
GPCR NaVa database	http://nava.liacs.nl/	Netherlands	Protein sequence databases
GPCRDB	http://www.gpcr.org/7tm/	Netherlands	Protein sequence databases
HGVS Databases	http://www.hgvs.org/	Netherlands	Human Genes and Diseases
NRG-CING	http://nmr.cmbi.ru.nl/NRG-CING	Netherlands	Structure Databases
NucleaRDB	http://www.receptors.org/NR/	Netherlands	Protein sequence databases
PhyloPat	http://www.cmbi.ru.nl/phylopat/	Netherlands	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
ProRepeat	http://prorepeat.bioinformatics.nl/	Netherlands	Protein sequence databases
SporeWeb	http://sporeweb.molgenrug.nl	Netherlands	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
WormQTL	http://www.wormqtl.org	Netherlands	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
WormQTLHD	http://www.wormqtl-hd.org	Netherlands	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
SuperCAT	http://mlstoslo.uio.no/	Norway	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
5S Ribosomal RNA Database	http://biobases.ibch.poznan.pl/5SData/	Poland	RNA sequence databases
Aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase database	http://rose.man.poznan.pl/aars/index.html	Poland	Protein sequence databases
BSDB	http://info.ifpan.edu.pl/BSDB/	Poland	Structure Databases
DNATraffic	http://dnatraffic.ibb.waw.pl/	Poland	Cell biology
miREX	http://bioinfo.amu.edu.pl/mirex	Poland	RNA sequence databases
miRNEST	http://mirnest.amu.edu.pl	Poland	RNA sequence databases
MODOMICS	http://genesilico.pl/modomics/	Poland	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, RNA sequence databases
ncRNAs database	http://biobases.ibch.poznan.pl/ncRNA/	Poland	RNA sequence databases
REPAIRtoire	http://repairtoire.genesilico.pl	Poland	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
RNA Bricks	http://iimcb.genesilico.pl/rnabricks	Poland	Structure Databases
RNA FRABASE	http://rnafrabase.ibch.poznan.pl/	Poland	RNA sequence databases, Structure Databases
RNAPathwaysDB	http://rnb.genesilico.pl/	Poland	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways

YEASTRACT	http://www.yeasttract.com/	Portugal	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Nucleotide Sequence Databases
phiSITE	http://www.phisite.org	Slovakia	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
GoMapMan	http://www.gomapman.org	Slovenia	Plant databases
3D-Footprint	http://floresta.eead.csic.es/3dpwm/	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
3DID - 3D interacting domains	http://3did.irbbarcelona.org/	Spain	Structure Databases
ABS	http://genome.crg.es/datasets/abs2005/	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
APPRIS	http://appris.bioinfo.cnio.es/	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
ArchDB	http://sbi.imim.es/ArchDB14	Spain	Structure Databases
Bionemo	http://bionemo.bioinfo.cnio.es/	Spain	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
CentrosomeDB	http://centrosome.cnb.csic.es	Spain	Protein sequence databases
ChiTaRS	http://chimerasrch.bioinfo.cnio.es/	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Degradome Database	http://degradome.uniovi.es/	Spain	Protein sequence databases
Drosophila polymorphism database	http://dpdb.uab.es/	Spain	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
EciD	http://ecid.bioinfo.cnio.es/	Spain	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
FCP	http://cgl.imim.es/fcp/	Spain	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Protein sequence databases
FireDB	http://firedb.bioinfo.cnio.es/	Spain	Protein sequence databases
HEG-DB	http://genomes.urv.cat/HEG-DB/	Spain	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HGT-DB, Horizontal Gene Transfer-DataBase	http://genomes.urv.es/HGT-DB/	Spain	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
InvFEST	http://invfestdb.uab.cat	Spain	Human Genes and Diseases
MamPol	http://mampol.uab.es/	Spain	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
MetaRouter	http://pdg.cnb.uam.es/MetaRouter/	Spain	Other Molecular Biology Databases
MultiTaskDB	http://wallace.uab.es/multitask/	Spain	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
NGSmethDB	http://bioinfo2.ugr.es/meth/NGSmethDB.php	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
PhylomeDB	http://www.phylomedb.org	Spain	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
RISSC - Ribosomal Internal Spacer Sequence Collection	http://egg.umh.es/rissc/	Spain	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), RNA sequence databases
TrSDB	http://ibb.uab.es/trsdb/	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
U12DB	http://genome.crg.es/cgi-bin/u12db/u12db.cgi	Spain	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
UniTrap	http://unitrap.crg.es/	Spain	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
BacMet	http://bacmet.biomedicine.gu.se/	Sweden	Other Molecular Biology Databases
FunCoup	http://funcoup.sbc.su.se/	Sweden	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways

FunShift	http://FunShift.cgb.ki.se/	Sweden	Protein sequence databases
HIC-Up	http://xray.bmc.uu.se/hicup/	Sweden	Structure Databases
Homeobox Page	http://www.biosci.ki.se/groups/tbu/homeo.html	Sweden	Protein sequence databases
Human MtDB	http://www.genpat.uu.se/mtDB/	Sweden	Organelle databases
Inparanoid	http://InParanoid.sbc.su.se/	Sweden	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PROPHECY	http://prophecy.lundberg.gu.se/	Sweden	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PTCH1 Mutation Database	http://www.cybergene.se/cgi-bin/w3-mysql/ptchbase/index.html	Sweden	Human Genes and Diseases
RNRdb	http://rnrdm.molbio.su.se/	Sweden	Protein sequence databases
siRNAdb	http://sirna.sbc.su.se/	Sweden	RNA sequence databases
AGD - Ashbya Genome Database	http://agd.vital-it.ch/	Switzerland	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CleanEx	http://cleanex.vital-it.ch/	Switzerland	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
CLIPZ	http://www.clipz.unibas.ch/	Switzerland	Protein sequence databases
Comparative Genometrics	http://www.unil.ch/comparativegenometrics/	Switzerland	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
ENZYME	http://www.expasy.org/enzyme/	Switzerland	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
EPD	http://epd.vital-it.ch/	Switzerland	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
HAMAP	http://www.expasy.org/sprot/hamap/	Switzerland	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Hits	http://hits.isb-sib.ch/	Switzerland	Protein sequence databases
HTPSELEX	http://ccg.vital-it.ch/htpselex/	Switzerland	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
MINAS	http://www.minas.uzh.ch	Switzerland	Structure Databases
miROrtho	http://cegg.unige.ch/mirortho/	Switzerland	RNA sequence databases
neXtProt	http://www.nextprot.org/	Switzerland	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
OMA	http://www.omabrowser.org	Switzerland	Protein sequence databases
OrthoDB	http://cegg.unige.ch/orthodb/browse	Switzerland	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Protein sequence databases
PLprot	http://www.plprot.ethz.ch/	Switzerland	Organelle databases, Plant databases
Progenetix	http://www.progenetix.org	Switzerland	Human Genes and Diseases
ProRule	http://www.expasy.org/tools/scanprosite/	Switzerland	Protein sequence databases
PROSITE	http://www.expasy.org/prosite/	Switzerland	Protein sequence databases
Selectome	http://bioinfo.unil.ch/selectome/	Switzerland	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human Genes and Diseases
SWISS-2DPAGE	http://www.expasy.org/ch2d/	Switzerland	Proteomics Resources
SwissBioisostere	http://www.swissbioisostere.ch/	Switzerland	Other Molecular Biology Databases
SWISS-MODEL Repository	http://swissmodel.expasy.org/repository/	Switzerland	Structure Databases

SwissRegulon	http://www.swissregulon.unibas.ch/	Switzerland	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
SwissSidechain	http://www.swissidechain.ch	Switzerland	Protein sequence databases
trome, trEST and trGEN	ftp://ftp.isrec.isb-sib.ch/pub/databases/	Switzerland	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
UCNEbase	http://ccg.vital-it.ch/UCNEbase/	Switzerland	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
ViralZone	http://viralzone.expasy.org/	Switzerland	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HotRegion	http://prism.cccb.ku.edu.tr/hotregion	Turkey	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
HotSprint	http://prism.cccb.ku.edu.tr/hotsprint/	Turkey	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Structure Databases
mESAdb	http://konulab.fen.bilkent.edu.tr/mirna/	Turkey	RNA sequence databases
Protein-protein interfaces	http://home.ku.edu.tr/~okeskin/INTERFACE/INTERFACES.html	Turkey	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
3D-Genomics	http://www.sbg.bio.ic.ac.uk/3dgenomics	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
ACeDB	http://www.acedb.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
Arabidopsis Nucleolar Protein Database	http://bioinf.scri.sari.ac.uk/cgi-bin/atnopdb/proteome_comparison/	United Kingdom	Plant databases
ArkDB	http://www.thearkdb.org/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
ArrayExpress	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
Aspergillus Genomes	http://www.aspergillus-genomes.org.uk/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
ASTD	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/astd/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
BioModels	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/biomodels/	United Kingdom	Other Molecular Biology Databases
BioSample	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
BloodExpress	http://hscl.cimr.cam.ac.uk/bloodexpress/	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
BuchneraBase	http://www.buchnera.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
C. elegans Project	http://www.sanger.ac.uk/Projects/C_elegans/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CADRE - Central Aspergillus Data Repository	http://www.cadre-genomes.org.uk	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CanSAR	http://cansar.icr.ac.uk	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
CAPS-DB	http://www.bioinsilico.org/CAPSDB	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
CATH	http://www.cathdb.info/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
CC+	http://coiledcoils.chm.bris.ac.uk/ccplus/search/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
ChEBI - Chemical Entities of Biological Interest	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
ChEMBL	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/db/	United Kingdom	Other Molecular Biology Databases
CluSTr	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/clustr/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
COGEME Phytopathogenic Fungi and Oomycete EST Database	http://cogeme.ex.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
CoGenT++	http://cgg.ebi.ac.uk/cgg/cpp_sitemap.html	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)

coliBase	http://colibase.bham.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Collagen Mutation Database	http://www.le.ac.uk/genetics/collagen/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
COMe - Co-Ordination of Metals etc.	http://www.flymine.org/come/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
COSMIC - Catalogue Of Somatic Mutations In Cancer	http://www.sanger.ac.uk/genetics/CGP/cosmic/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
CSA - Catalytic Site Atlas	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/thornton-srv/databases/CSA/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
CSD - Cambridge Structural Database	http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/prods/csd/csd.html	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
D2P2	http://d2p2.pro	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
Database of Genomic Variants archive (DGVa)	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/dgva/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
DBASS5/3	http://www.dbass.org.uk/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
DBD	http://www.transcriptionfactor.org/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
dcGO	http://supfam.org/SUPERFAMILY/dcGO	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
DECIPHER	http://decipher.sanger.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
DPVweb	http://www.dpvweb.net/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
DRASTIC	http://www.drastic.org.uk/	United Kingdom	Plant databases
EBI Enzyme Portal	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/enzymeportal	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
EBI Genomes	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/genomes/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
EBI Metagenomics	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
EBI patent sequences	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/patentdata/nr/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Edinburgh Mouse (EMAP) Atlas	http://www.emouseatlas.org/Atlas/intro.html	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
EDULISS	http://eduliss.bch.ed.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
EMAGE	http://www.emouseatlas.org/emage/	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
EMMA	http://www.emmanet.org	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
Ensembl	http://www.ensembl.org/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
Enzyme Nomenclature	http://www.chem.qmul.ac.uk/iubmb/enzyme/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Europe PubMed Central	http://europepmc.org/	United Kingdom	Other Molecular Biology Databases
European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA)	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ega/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
European Nucleotide Archive	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
EuroPhenome	http://www.europhenome.org/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
Expression Atlas	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
EyeSite	http://eyesite.cryst.bbk.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
FLIGHT	http://flight.icr.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases

FlyAtlas	http://flyatlas.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FlyMine	http://www.flymine.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FlyTF	http://www.flytf.org/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases, Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
FunTree	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/thornton-srv/databases/FunTree/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
G2Cdb	http://www.genes2cognition.org/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
GDSC	http://www.cancerRxgene.org	United Kingdom	Other Molecular Biology Databases
GenAtlas	http://www.genatlas.org/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
Gene3D	http://cathwww.biochem.ucl.ac.uk:8080/Gene3D/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
GeneDB	http://www.genedb.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Genome Reviews	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/GenomeReviews/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
Genome3D	http://beta.genome3d.eu	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
Genomic Threading Database	http://gene3d.biochem.ucl.ac.uk/Gene3D/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
GPX-Macrophage Expression Atlas	http://gpxmea.gti.ed.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Immunological databases, Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
GWAS Central	https://www.gwascentral.org/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
HaemB	http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/petergreen/haemBdatabase.html	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
HepSeq	http://www.hpa-bioinformatics.org.uk/HepSEQ-Research/Public/Web_Front/main.php	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
HGNC Database	http://www.genenames.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Human Genes and Diseases
Human PAX6 Allelic Variant Database	http://pax6.hgu.mrc.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
IKMC	http://www.knockoutmouse.org/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
IMGT/HLA	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/imgt/hla/	United Kingdom	Immunological databases
IMPC	http://www.mousephenotype.org	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
IntAct	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/intact/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Integr8 (formerly Proteome Analysis Database)	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/integr8/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
IntEnz	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/intenz/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
InterPro	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/interpro/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
IPD - Immuno Polymorphism Database	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ipd/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
IPD-ESTDAB	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ipd/estdab/	United Kingdom	Immunological databases
IPD-HPA - Human Platelet Antigens	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ipd/hpa/	United Kingdom	Immunological databases
IPD-KIR - Killer-cell Immunoglobulin-like Receptors	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ipd/kir/	United Kingdom	Immunological databases
IPD-MHC	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ipd/mhc/	United Kingdom	Immunological databases

iPfam	http://ipfam.sanger.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
IPI - International Protein Index	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/IPI	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
IUBMB Nomenclature database	http://www.chem.qmul.ac.uk/iubmb/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
IUPAC Nomenclature database	http://www.chem.qmul.ac.uk/iupac/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
IUPHAR-DB	http://www.iuphar-db.org/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
IUPHAR-RD	http://www.iuphar-db.org/iuphar-rd/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Other Molecular Biology Databases
JASPAR	http://jaspar.genereg.net/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Kidney Development Database	http://golgi.ana.ed.ac.uk/kidhome.html	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
Kinomer	http://www.compbio.dundee.ac.uk/kinomer/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
LAMP	http://www.llamp.net	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
LGICdb	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/compneur-srv/LGICdb/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
Locus-specific variation database	http://lsdb.hgu.mrc.ac.uk/home.php	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
LumbriBASE	http://www.earthworms.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
MACiE	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/thornton-srv/databases/MACiE/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
MEROPS	http://merops.sanger.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
MetaboLights	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/MetaboLights	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
metaTIGER	http://www.bioinformatics.leeds.ac.uk/metatiger/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
miRBase	http://www.mirbase.org/	United Kingdom	RNA sequence databases
MIRIAM Registry?	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/miriam/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
MitoMiner	http://mitominer.mrc-mbu.cam.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Organelle databases
modMine	http://intermine.modencode.org	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases
MoKCa	http://strubiol.icr.ac.uk/extra/mokca/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
Mousebook	http://www.mousebook.org/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
NASCarrays	http://affymetrix.arabidopsis.info/	United Kingdom	Microarray Data and other Gene Expression Databases, Plant databases
NCL Resource	http://www.ucl.ac.uk/ncl/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
Nematodes.org	http://www.nematodes.org/nematodegenomes/index.php/Main_Page	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
NEMBASE	http://www.nematodes.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
NOPdb: Nucleolar Proteome Database	http://www.lamondlab.com/NOPdb/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
NPD - Nuclear Protein Database	http://npd.hgu.mrc.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
OPTIC	http://genserv.anat.ox.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Protein sequence databases

OriDB - The DNA Replication Origin Database	http://www.oridb.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate), Nucleotide Sequence Databases
Pancreas Expression	http://www.pancreasexpression.org	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
PANDIT	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/goldman-srv/pandit/	United Kingdom	Nucleotide Sequence Databases, Protein sequence databases
PathBase	http://www.pathbase.net/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
PCDDB	http://pcddb.cryst.bbk.ac.uk	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
PCRPI-DB	http://www.bioinsilico.org/PCRPIDB	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
PDBe	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
PDBsum	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbsum	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
PepSeeker	http://nwsr.smith.man.ac.uk/pepseeker/	United Kingdom	Proteomics Resources
Peptaibol	http://peptaibol.cryst.bbk.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Other Molecular Biology Databases, Protein sequence databases
Pfam	http://pfam.sanger.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
PIPs	http://www.compbio.dundee.ac.uk/www-pips/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
Plant DNA C-values database	http://www.kew.org/genomesize/homepage.html	United Kingdom	Plant databases
Plant snoRNA DB	http://bioinf.scri.sari.ac.uk/cgi-bin/plant_snorna/home	United Kingdom	Plant databases, RNA sequence databases
PomBase	http://www.pombase.org/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
PRIDE	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/	United Kingdom	Proteomics Resources
PRINTS	http://www.bioinf.man.ac.uk/dbbrowser/PRINTS/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
PROCOGNATE	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/thornton-srv/databases/procognate/index.html	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
pSTIING	http://pstiing.icr.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
RESID	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/RESID/	United Kingdom	Proteomics Resources, Structure Databases
Rfam	http://rfam.sanger.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	RNA sequence databases, Structure Databases
Rhea	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/rhea/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways
RNA Virus Database	http://virus.zoo.ox.ac.uk/rnavirusdb/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
SAbDab	http://opig.stats.ox.ac.uk/webapps/sabdab	United Kingdom	Immunological databases
SCOP2 - Structural Classification Of Proteins	http://scop.mrc-lmb.cam.ac.uk/scop	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
SCOPPI	http://www.scoppi.org/	United Kingdom	Metabolic and Signaling Pathways, Structure Databases
SIFTS	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/docs/sifts/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
SISYPHUS	http://sisyphus.mrc-cpe.cam.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases, Structure Databases
SitesBase	http://www.modelling.leeds.ac.uk/sb/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases, Structure Databases
SNAPPI	http://www.compbio.dundee.ac.uk/SNAPPI/downloads.jsp	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
SNPSTR	http://www3.imperial.ac.uk/theoreticalgenomics/data-software/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes, Nucleotide Sequence Databases

SUPERFAMILY	http://supfam.org/	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
Sure-ChEMBL	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/surechembl	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
T1DBase - Type 1 Diabetes Database	http://t1dbase.org/	United Kingdom	Human Genes and Diseases
TOPS - Topology Of Protein Structures	http://www.tops.leeds.ac.uk	United Kingdom	Structure Databases
TRBase	http://trbase.ex.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
TreeFam	http://www.treefam.org/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
UniProt	http://www.uniprot.org/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
UniProtKB - Gene Ontology Annotation	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/GOA/	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
UniSave	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/uniprot/unisave/	United Kingdom	Protein sequence databases
VEGA	http://vega.sanger.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes
VIDA	http://www.biochem.ucl.ac.uk/bsm/virus_database/VIDA.html	United Kingdom	Genomics Databases (non-vertebrate)
X:MAP	http://annmap.picr.man.ac.uk/	United Kingdom	Human and other Vertebrate Genomes